

Project Promotion Materials

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Executive Summary

Rare-earth (RE) permanent magnets based on neodymium-iron-boron (Nd-Fe-B) are essential parts of electric vehicles and wind turbines, making them central to Europe's green energy future. While these magnets offer exceptional performance, they also present challenges – chief among them Europe's dependence on external imports.

In June 2024, the GREENE project – SINGLE-GRAIN RE-ENGINEERED ND-FE-B PERMANENT MAGNETS – was launched by a consortium of 15 European partners, led by the Jožef Stefan Institute, with €8 million in EU funding, for a period of 4 years. The project aims to revolutionize Nd-Fe-B magnets by re-engineering them at the single-grain level to reduce RE content, using both virgin and recycled feedstocks, and minimizing environmental impact and supply chain dependencies. GREENE's ultimate goal is to deliver more resource-efficient magnets with enhanced properties and establish an operational manufacturing system for these innovations.

This document compiles the promotional materials developed in the context of the project. It will remain a living document until the project's conclusion, at which point all materials will have been finalised and it will be published as **Deliverable D8.5 – GREENE promotion materials in Zenodo.**

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1. GREENE Flyer

Figure 1: GREENE flyer front and back

The GREENE flyer has been designed in a practical postcard (A6) format and presents key project information, including the project name, a brief summary, essential data and partner logos. It also features a QR code linking to the GREENE website for further details and is intended to be printed on plantable seed paper.

2. GREENE Roll-Up

Figure 2: GREENE roll-up

The GREENE roll-ups is designed for use at events to promote the project as part of a booth setup and follows a standard format. It displays the project’s goals, key facts, partner logos and includes a QR code linking to the website.

3. GREENE General Poster

SINGLE-GRAIN RE-ENGINEERED ND-FE-B PERMANENT MAGNETS

GREENE is an EU-funded project focused on pioneering advancements in high-performance permanent magnets, re-engineering their microstructure to make them powerful while at the same time reducing Rare Earth (RE) content. The project is tackling the environmental and supply challenges associated with these crucial components of high-tech products that power a green energy future, such as e-vehicles and wind turbines.

KEY FACTS

€8 Mio EU-Funding (Horizon Europe)

15 Partners from 10 European Countries

4 Years (1st June 2024 until 31st May 2028)

CONCEPT

CONSORTIUM

COORDINATOR: Jožef Stefan Institute; Prof. Kristina Žužek

greene-project.eu
GREENE Project

Figure 3: Poster version 1

SINGLE-GRAIN RE-ENGINEERED ND-FE-B PERMANENT MAGNETS

GREENE is an EU-funded project aimed at advancing high-performance permanent magnets by redesigning their microstructure. The project focuses on producing powerful magnets while reducing the use of Rare Earth elements, addressing both environmental concerns and supply chain risks. These innovations are critical for enabling the next generation of green technologies, including electric vehicles and wind turbines.

KEY FACTS

€8 Mio EU-Funding (Horizon Europe)

15 Partners from 10 European Countries

4 Years (1st June 2024 until 31st May 2028)

CONCEPT

A complete value chain

CONSORTIUM

COORDINATOR: Jožef Stefan Institute; Prof. Kristina Žužek

greene-project.eu
GREENE Project

Figure 4: Poster version 2

The GREENE general poster has been developed in two versions. Both provide a concise overview of the project, including key facts, consortium partner logos and a QR code linking to the website. They differ in the visual approach used to illustrate the concept: one highlights grain boundary optimization, while the other focuses on the entire value chain. The poster is intended for use at

conferences and events where a general overview of the project is presented, rather than focusing on a specific scientific aspect.

4. General Project Presentation

<p>greene Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Single-grain Re-engineered Nd-Fe-B Permanent Magnets</p> <p>Maëva Pratloug Senior Project Manager Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (SEZ)</p> <p>Eva Kopf Project Manager Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (SEZ)</p>	<p>GREENE IN A NUTSHELL</p> <p>Main goal: Tackling the environmental and supply challenges associated with permanent magnets as crucial components of many products that power a green energy future, e.g. wind turbines and electric vehicles</p> <p>How: Pioneering advancements in high-performance permanent magnets, by re-engineering their microstructure to make them more powerful while at the same time reducing rare earths content as critical / strategic materials</p> <p>8 Million EUR Funding</p> <p>15 Partners from 10 European Countries</p> <p>4 Years June 2024 – May 2028</p> <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>
<p>PROJECT GOALS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource efficient, high-performance Nd-Fe-B magnets with -20% RE content, +20% coercivity, and maximum energy product +20% Independent, resilient and scalable supply of key materials, magnets and components within Europe Increased sustainability of magnet production with -5% scrap rates, -15% energy consumed and -30% toxicity Society and stakeholders better equipped for a sustainable green transition in Europe <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>GREENE CONCEPT Advanced material models and simulation</p> <p>Simulations at all scales cover the chemical, mechanical, and magnetic properties of material interfaces in bulk magnets.</p> <p>A detailed understanding of the local physics and chemistry helps design grain-boundary phases to enhance coercivity.</p> <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>
<p>GREENE CONCEPT Redesigned rare-earth magnets</p> <p>Models & Simulation → Optimisation of the grain boundary & Production of magnets with enhanced properties and less critical materials</p> <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>GREENE CONCEPT A complete value chain</p> <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>
<p>GREENE PARTNERS MAIN ROLES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination: Jožef Stefan Institute Permanent Magnets and Material Science: HS PF, Hochschule Aalen, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche Magnetism at Interfaces: CNRS, TU Braunschweig Advanced Nanoscale Analysis: CSIC, Universidad Zaragoza Sustainability Analysis: Universiteit Leiden, The Netherlands Industrialisation: IMAGNETI, HYPRMAG, BOSCH Outreach, IP & Strategies for Use of Results: Universiteit Leiden, The Netherlands <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>WIDER IMPACTS Sustainability and Industrial Leadership</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing scalable advanced materials to address societal and technological challenges Enabling more recycling of critical / strategic materials Helping industries to lower emissions, energy consumption, and negative impacts on people and environment related to current production Supporting digital transformation of European materials and magnet production Positioning Europe at the forefront of sustainable innovation <p>greene Funded by the European Union</p>

<p>WIDER IMPACTS Autonomy and Resilience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing European dependencies on third countries for critical / strategic materials • Encouraging sector-wide, deep transformations aligning with EU 2050 goals to become a climate-neutral, circular, and competitive economy • Enhancing opportunities for new markets, products, and services • Advancing the competitiveness and leadership of European industries <p>greene Funded by the European Union 9</p>	<p>WIDER IMPACTS Scientific and Socioeconomic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bringing together various disciplines to generate high-quality knowledge in magnetic interfaces on an atomic scale • Positioning Europe at the forefront of science and innovation in the field of rare earth elements, magnetic materials and permanent magnets • Addressing skill gaps and contributing to improved employment and social conditions across Europe • Fostering cross-sectoral advancements by exploring synergies with related projects and initiatives <p>greene Funded by the European Union 10</p>
<p>GREENE CONSORTIUM</p> <p>greene Funded by the European Union 11</p>	<p>POSSIBLE SYNERGIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainability analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e.g. baseline LCA, joint non-sensitive/confidential data, environmental impact in REE value chains 'Talking Magnets' (online) seminar series <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • with e.g. presentations, discussions, exercises, reading recommendations • mainly for academic students and junior professionals (research/industry) • materials and recordings available in Zenodo, if possible Policy recommendations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GREENE input for e.g. national implementation of CRM Act; obstacles and opportunities for the future of the European REE value chain... Standardisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e.g. contribution to WS/TC such as CEN/TC 472 REE and its technical specifications for the labelling of products containing one or more permanent magnets Joint Communication & Dissemination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in GREENE channels • any further opportunity / request: Don't hesitate to get in touch! Interactive learning tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for wider public • on- and offline • e.g. infographic, quiz, magnet experiments Science communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events and activities aimed at the wider public • Open lab days, public events (open days, girls' day etc.) European School of Magnetism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expert talks • Student participation <p>greene Funded by the European Union 12</p>
<p>Thank you for your attention!</p> <p> GREENE Project greene-project.eu</p> <p>Contacts:</p> <p>Maëva Pratlong Senior Project Manager Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (SEZ) maeva.pratlong@steinbeis-europa.de</p> <p>Eva Kopf Project Manager Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (SEZ) eva.kopf@steinbeis-europa.de</p> <p>SCAN ME</p> <p>Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement N° 101129888. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the HaDEA can be held responsible for them.</p> <p>greene Funded by the European Union 14</p>	

Figure 5: General project presentation

The general project presentation is designed for use at events and meetings, where a general overview of the project is required. It begins with a concise summary (GREENE in a nutshell), followed by an introduction to the project objectives and overall concept, from material modelling and simulation to the full value chain. It then presents the partners and their respective roles and addresses the broader impacts, as well as potential synergies with related projects and initiatives.

5. Visuals and Infographics

5.1 Key Background Visual

Figure 6: Key background visual

As a key element of the project identity, the GREENE key background visual is used in a number of promotional materials. It illustrates the diverse applications of magnets, found in flatscreens, speakers, electric car, trains, hard disk drives, pump motors, washing machines and wind turbines. Like the logo, it is kept geometrically simple with an added magnet pattern that emphasizes the theme.

5.2 Grain Boundary Diffusion

Figure 7: Infographic grain boundary diffusion

This infographic compares three approaches to grain boundary diffusion processing (GBDP) for Nd-Fe-B magnets. It first shows the conventional method, where a diffusion source is applied to the magnet surface and diffuses over millimetre-scale thicknesses, modifying the Nd-rich phase around the Nd₂Fe₁₄B matrix phase. It then illustrates conventional in-situ GBDP, where Nd-Fe-B powder is processed with a metal Dy vapour and diffusion source, leading to Nd-rich phases around the magnetic matrix at micrometre scale. Finally, the GREENE single-grain in-situ GBDP approach is presented as a novel route in which specially designed grain boundary precursors

form new GREENE grain boundary phases around individual $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ grains, enabling targeted modification at the single-grain level.

5.3 Grain Boundary Recreation

Figure 8: Infographic grain boundary recreation

This infographic illustrates how the GREENE approach aims to recreate and optimise the grain boundary structure in Nd-Fe-B magnets. Starting from the original magnet composition, advanced modelling is used to design novel grain boundary precursors that improve the interaction between individual $\text{Nd}_2\text{Fe}_{14}\text{B}$ grains and the surrounding grain boundary phases. By tailoring these interfaces, GREENE seeks to enhance key magnetic properties such as remanence and coercivity, while reducing the need for critical materials.

5.4 Computational Modelling

Figure 9: GREENE computational modelling visual

This visual represents the computational modelling applied in GREENE to optimise grain boundaries in magnets showing a magnet alongside its internal grain boundary structure.

5.5 Pilot Line

Figure 10: GREENE beta prototype permanent magnets production

This visual illustrates all steps of the GREENE beta prototype permanent magnet production line, from mining (primary or secondary sources) to the integration and testing of the final magnet. The production concept is based on a modular set-up, enabling each process step to operate

independently and to be replaced or upgraded as more advanced technologies and knowledge emerge beyond the project.

6. Sticker for Equipment and Demonstrators

Figure 11: GREENE sticker design for equipment and demonstrators

The sticker design for equipment and demonstrators has been developed to fulfil funding acknowledgement requirements while maintaining the GREENE visual identity. It can be printed in various sizes, depending on the specific equipment. The QR code links to the GREENE website.

Annex: About the Project Partners

To achieve the ambitious undertaking of GREENE, 15 European partners with outstanding expertise in their respective fields have joined forces, including leading material scientists, magnet manufacturers and recyclers, lifecycle analysis experts as well as end user representatives.

**Jožef Stefan
Institute**

The [Jožef Stefan Institute](#) (JSI), Slovenia's largest research institute, spans a wide range of disciplines including physics, chemistry, molecular biology, biotechnology, reactor physics, energy and environmental studies. The institute's [Department for Nanostructured Materials](#) coordinates the collaborative efforts within the GREENE project, leveraging its extensive expertise and advanced equipment to conduct world-class research on permanent magnets. JSI's contributions to GREENE are centred on its core competencies in Density-Functional-Theory calculations, materials science synthesis and tailoring of Nd-Fe-B microstructures, fresh feedstock production and rapid solidification techniques in a protective atmosphere. Moreover, JSI is responsible for setting up the GREENE beta prototype permanent magnets production.

HS PF

The [Institute for Precious and Technology Metals](#) at [Pforzheim University of Applied Sciences](#) (HSPF) is a leading research center with over 30 years of expertise in advanced magnetic materials and metallurgical processes.

In the context of GREENE, HSPF is spearheading the development and production of recycled and innovative feedstocks for permanent magnets. The research focuses on optimising the processes of powder milling, powder morphology and hydrogen processing of magnet scrap (HPMS), employing advanced techniques such as NeoLeach treatment of powders to produce feedstocks with micro- and nano-scale grain structures.

University for
Continuing
Education KREMS

The [University for Continuing Education KREMS](#) (DUK)'s [Department of Integrated Sensor Systems](#) boasts decades of experience in magnetic sensors and permanent magnet design. Their advanced micromagnetic simulations incorporate local chemistry and structural influences on magnetic properties. In GREENE, DUK will model and simulate the mechanical properties of magnetic materials to develop innovative grain boundaries, collaborating closely with partners to integrate thermal and physical strain data into their models.

**Universidad
Zaragoza**

CSIC

CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

The [Instituto de Nanociencia y Materiales de Aragón](#), one of the leading materials research institutes in Spain, was established through a partnership between the [Universidad de Zaragoza](#) (UNIZAR) and the [Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas](#) (CSIC). This joint institute's expertise, along with its state-of-the-art transmission electron microscope facilities, plays a pivotal role in analysing the nanoscale

structure, chemistry and magnetism of the redesigned Nd-Fe-B magnets in GREENE. Their contributions are essential to the development and monitoring of novel materials throughout the project.

The [Materials Research Institute](#) of [Aalen University](#) (HTW AALEN) specialises in the development of functional materials, with a particular focus on electromobility and renewable energy. HTW AALEN employs high-throughput methods to discover novel, sustainable magnetic materials and integrates cutting-edge technologies such as additive manufacturing and recycling. Additionally, the institute leverages artificial intelligence and machine learning to enhance its research capabilities. In GREENE, HTW AALEN offers specialised expertise in calculating intrinsic Nd-Fe-B properties, casts pure Nd₂Fe₁₄B phase and contributes thermodynamic phase equilibria models.

The Department of Strength of Materials, Theoretical Mechanics, and Engineering Graphics of [Vinnytsia National Technical University](#) (VNTU), one of Ukraine's leading universities, is known for its expertise in polycrystalline body mechanics modelling and investigation of mechanical strain-stress. In collaboration with CNRS-IJL and TUW, VNTU contributes to addressing magnetism challenges through strain calculations in GREENE. These calculations are vital for resolving paradoxes in conventional magnetism theories and manufacturing processes.

[The Institute Jean Lamour](#) (IJL) is a material science research laboratory operated by [CNRS](#) and [Université de Lorraine](#). IJL studies model surfaces of Nd-Fe-B as well as model interfaces using advanced techniques under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions and ultra-thin film deposition. Additionally, their research on new grain-boundary coatings provides valuable information for various aspects of the project.

[Magneti Ljubljana](#) (MAGNETI), a European manufacturer of permanent magnets with over 65 years of expertise, brings invaluable industrial know-how to the project. With a dedicated production line for sintering commercial-grade Nd-Fe-B permanent magnets, MAGNETI offers a crucial perspective on the path to industrialisation following the project's completion.

[Steinbeis Europa Zentrum](#) (SEZ) has extensive experience in innovation consulting with a focus on international markets and EU research funding. In GREENE, SEZ supports project partners in defining result pathways, managing intellectual property, and ensuring that project outcomes are visible and accessible to a broad audience. SEZ is also responsible for

communication and awareness raising activities and provides administrative and financial management support.

[Leiden University's \(ULEI\) Institute of Environmental Sciences](#) specialises in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methods to assess emerging technological setups, supporting decision-making for sustainability. It is renowned for its proficiency in methodologies such as Material Flow Analysis and Accounting with significant experience in the field of critical raw materials. In GREENE, ULEI conducts a comprehensive sustainability assessment.

[The Institute of Materials for Electronics and Magnetism](#) of Italy's leading public research organisation [Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche](#) (CNR) specialises in material science with a focus on synthesis, characterisation, modelling, and device prototyping. In GREENE, they contribute their expertise in magnetic characterisation of powders and magnets, particularly through singular point measurements, analysing magnetic properties under high magnetic fields and optimising the performance of advanced materials.

The [Technische Universität Wien](#) (TUW) is Austria's largest research and educational institution specialising in technology and natural sciences. The Functional Materials group at the [Institute of Solid-State Physics](#) is a key scientific partner in GREENE, focusing on interface engineering of granular feedstocks.

[HyProMag](#) (HMG) is a technology start-up founded in 2021 as a spin-off of Pforzheim University. It specializes in reprocessing RE permanent magnets with a focus on producing magnetic powders, alloys, and sintered magnets for high-tech EU applications. The company offers consulting on recycling-friendly design and uses the IP-protected Hydrogen Processing of Magnet Scrap (HPMS) and other technologies for eco-friendly scrap dismantling and powder processing. In GREENE, HMG produces recycled feedstock in synergy with Pforzheim University.

Robert [Bosch](#) GmbH drive sustainability in mobility through high-quality products and innovative electrified solutions. Expertise includes power electronics, electric motors, eAxle systems, comfort actuators, and charging solutions. The divisions also offer electromechanical systems for e-bikes, passenger cars, and commercial vehicles, along with thermal and wiper systems and vehicle stabilization applications. As technology co-developer, Bosch will support the production and testing of demonstrators and contribute to design for recycling and sustainability and economic assessment in GREENE.